

Optimizing Pix2Pix for Comics: A Study on Static vs. Dynamic Loss Weighting

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Abstract

We introduce ComicGAN, a modified Pix2Pix-based architecture tailored for translating comic images. Our method incorporates comparing static to adaptive loss weighting via varying the proportionality constant (λ) to balance adversarial and reconstruction losses. We compare experiments using fixed versus dynamic lambda strategies and assess their impact on image quality and training stability. The results indicate that the static lambda adjustment improves both the convergence and the fidelity of generated comic-style images, and reveals interesting aspects on the mechanics of training GAN's.

1 Introduction

Recently, artificial intelligence has become more prominent in creative sectors as new models have become increasingly more effective in creating convincing imagery. The Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) is a tool that has been very useful in achieving this milestone. Goodfellow et al. defined the GAN as "a new framework for estimating generative models via an adversarial process, in which we simultaneously train two models: a generative model G that captures the data distribution and a discriminative model D that estimates the probability that a sample came from the training data rather than G ." (2014). This framework consists of a generator and a discriminator that interact with each other like competition, where the generator is finding new ways to fool the discriminator, and the discriminator is finding new ways to distinguish it from the actual training data; this process ideally leads to a generator that can create perfect imitations of the training data. The topic of this paper will be to investigate style transfer using GANs to create comic-styled pictures of selfies. To accomplish that, we have taken inspiration

from the Pix2Pix architecture described by Isola et al. in their paper named "Image-to-Image Translation with Conditional Adversarial Networks" (2016). This architecture uses a combination of the conditional GAN (cGAN) loss and the L1 loss as its loss function, with a value lambda (λ) controlling the weight of the L1 loss term. This paper investigates our process for finding the optimal lambda value for our model. The applications for this model are wide and varied, but an immediate use case could be filters for social media applications. Finding a lambda value that results in a model that creates high-quality images is crucial for this application. This paper will investigate the following question: "How do different static and dynamic lambda values influence the quality of generated comic images, and can a dynamic lambda strategy improve training stability and image quality compared to fixed values?" This question will be answered by providing a comparative analysis between static and dynamic lambda strategies.

2 Related Work

The framework used throughout this paper was inspired by the work of Isola et al. (2016). Their paper proposes a conditional GAN (cGAN) that consists of two components, the generator and the discriminator, as a general framework for image-to-image translation. Their generator uses a U-net architecture, and they justify their choice through their testing: "The encoder-decoder is unable to learn to generate realistic images in our experiments. The advantages of the U-Net appear not to be specific to conditional GANs: when both the U-Net and encoder-decoder are trained with an L1 loss, the U-Net again achieves the superior results." (Isola et al., 2016). Their discriminator uses the patchGAN architecture, which is an architecture that evaluates the image in local patches rather than evaluating the whole image at once.

3 Methodology

3.1 Pix2Pix Model Overview

Our generator is inspired by the U-Net architecture (Ronneberger et al., 2015), originally introduced for the segmentation of biomedical images. The U-Net structure provides an encoder-decoder framework with skip connections, allowing for both global context understanding and fine-grained spatial information preservation. Although Pix2Pix employs a standard U-Net as its generator, we extend this design by integrating additional residual blocks (He et al., 2015) and modifications to skip connections, improving the network’s ability to capture the intricate textures and structural details characteristic of comic images.

The encoder consists of eight downsampling convolutional layers (LeCun et al., 1998), where each downsample block halves the spatial resolution while increasing the number of feature channels. Notably, the first convolutional layer omits batch normalization (Ioffe et al., 2015) to better preserve raw image statistics. Where at the deepest feature level (bottleneck), the initial image is reduced to an extremely compressed feature map of dimensions $512 \times 2 \times 2$ from the initial $3 \times 512 \times 512$ image. This feature representation is further refined through a sequence of residual blocks, which are proven in larger models such as ResNet (He et al., 2015) to enhance the ability of the network to model complex transformations while mitigating vanishing gradients.

The decoder mirrors the encoder with a series of upsampling layers, progressively reconstructing the high-resolution output. Each upsampled feature map is concatenated with its corresponding encoder feature map via skip connections, ensuring the retention of fine-grained spatial details lost in downsampling. The final output layer employs a tanh activation to normalize the pixel values to the $[-1, 1]$ range, facilitating stable image generation. Additionally, dropout layers (Srivastava et al., 2014) in the deeper upsampling stages introduce regularization, reducing overfitting, and improving generalization. These architectural enhancements collectively enable our generator to produce visually coherent and detailed translations of input images into the target comic domain.

The discriminator is a simpler network that consists of 4 convolution layers followed by a batch normalization and LeakyRelu (Xu et al., 2015) activation function with a negative slope of 0.2. Except for the first layer, which has no batch normalization. All of

these convolutions consist of 4×4 kernels with a stride of 2 and a padding of 1, to maintain consistency with the generator. The final discriminator layer is another simple 4×4 convolution layer with a stride of 1 and no padding. This is then followed by a sigmoid (Narayan, 1997) activation function that enables our model to output a value between $[0, 1]$ for our binary classification of comic or not.

To learn more effectively, the model employs a combination of adversarial loss and pixel-wise reconstruction loss to guide the generator toward producing realistic outputs while preserving structural details. The adversarial loss is computed using the Binary Cross-Entropy (BCE) loss function, formulated as followed:

$$\mathcal{L}_{GAN}(G, D) = E_{x,y}[\log D(x, y)] + E_{x,z}[\log(1 - D(x, G(x, z)))] \quad (1)$$

where G represents the generator, D is the discriminator, x is the input image, y is the corresponding ground truth output, and z is the latent noise. This loss encourages the generator to produce outputs that the discriminator classifies as real. The discriminator loss is computed as the average of the real and fake losses:

$$\mathcal{L}_D = \frac{1}{2} [E_{x,y}[\mathcal{L}_{BCE}(D(x, y), 1)] + E_{x,z}[\mathcal{L}_{BCE}(D(x, G(x, z)), 0)]] \quad (2)$$

where \mathcal{L}_{BCE} denotes the Binary Cross-Entropy loss.

In addition to adversarial loss, the model incorporates an L1 pixelwise reconstruction loss to encourage structural similarity between the generated and target images. This loss is defined as follows:

$$\mathcal{L}_{L1}(G) = E_{x,y,z} [\|y - G(x, z)\|_1] \quad (3)$$

The final generator loss combines both terms, weighted by a hyperparameter λ :

$$\mathcal{L}_G = \mathcal{L}_{GAN} + \lambda \mathcal{L}_{L1} \quad (4)$$

The role of λ is crucial, as it balances the adversarial loss with the pixelwise reconstruction loss. A higher λ value emphasizes structural accuracy, leading to outputs that closely match the ground truth but may lack finer details, whereas a lower λ shifts the focus toward fooling the discriminator, potentially sacrificing content fidelity for more visually plausible textures. In addition, λ can be dynamically adjusted during training to refine convergence and optimize output quality.

$$G^* = \arg \min_G \max_D \mathcal{L}_{cGAN}(G, D) + \lambda \mathcal{L}_{L1}(G)$$

where $L_{cGAN}(G, D)$ represents the conditional GAN loss and $L_{L1}(G)$ represents the L1. Finally, λ is a hyperparameter that controls the weight of the L1 loss compared to the GAN loss.

3.2 Technical Setup

The dataset used in to train the network is a public Kaggle dataset titled "Comic faces (paired, synthetic v2)" (Petay, 2021). This dataset consists of 10,000 pairs of images, where one image is a regular selfie with a pair matching in the style of a comic. This creates a total of 20,000 images to be used during the training and testing process. Each of those images has a 1024x1024 dimension. These images were all synthetically generated: faces were generated by an FFHQ StyleGAN2, and comic faces were generated by another FFHQ StyleGAN2, fine-tuned on a comic dataset. Some faces in the dataset are purposely disfigured. The reason for this architectural choice was that disfigured images "tend to be useful for full image-to-comic conversion, as they teach models how to trace something if it is not a face." (Petay, 2021).

Each sample undergoes a series of preprocessing steps, including resizing to 512×512 , which drastically reduces computational complexity while not losing many features. This is a trade-off which has to be delicately struck, as too much of a reduction in dimensionality which is not learned can be lost features. The images then undergo normalization to the range $[-1, 1]$, and conversion to tensor format. The dataset is randomly shuffled and split into training and test sets, with 80% of the data allocated to training and 20% for testing.

During training, the model employs a batch size of 48, chosen to balance computational efficiency and stability. The optimization process is carried out using the Adam optimizer (Kingma et al., 2017), with a learning rate of 0.0002 and momentum parameters $\beta_1 = 0.5$ and $\beta_2 = 0.999$. These values are commonly used in GAN training, as they stabilize convergence by reducing oscillations in the optimization trajectory. The generator and discriminator are updated separately, with the generator aiming to minimize adversarial and pixel-wise reconstruction losses, while the discriminator learns to differentiate between real and generated images. The model is then trained for 50 epochs, a level that results in some model convergence while keeping the computation to a manageable

level in this context.

The choice of hyperparameters is critical to ensure stable training. The learning rate of 0.0002 is established based on empirical findings from prior GAN research, as higher values can lead to instability, while lower values can slow convergence. The momentum term $\beta_1 = 0.5$ is selected to prevent excessive dampening of updates, a common issue in adversarial training. Furthermore, $\beta_2 = 0.999$ is used to maintain an adaptive learning rate by adjusting for past gradient magnitudes. These hyperparameter selections, along with batch size and preprocessing steps, contribute to the overall performance and stability of the model during training.

3.3 Lambda Variation Strategies

Fixed Lambda Values: The original Pix2Pix architecture used fixed lambda values to balance adversarial and reconstruction loss terms. To find the right lambda values to examine, we used data from previous testing runs with manually chosen values. This helped us find the average adversarial and reconstruction losses over multiple training runs. This was then used to find lambda values that would represent: 25%, 50%, and 75% of these calculated averages.

$$\bar{\lambda} = \frac{\alpha \times \bar{\mathcal{L}}_{GAN}}{\bar{\mathcal{L}}_1 \times (1 - \alpha)} \quad (5)$$

where:

- $\bar{\mathcal{L}}_1$ is the average pixel loss,
- $\bar{\mathcal{L}}_{GAN}$ is the average adversarial loss, and
- α is the desired contribution of the pixel loss (expressed as a value between 0 and 1).

Dynamic Lambda Strategy: The purpose of adopting dynamic lambda values is to maintain that both loss terms contribute a fixed ratio to the overall generator loss.

As the absolute magnitudes of the reconstruction (\mathcal{L}_{L1}) loss and adversarial (\mathcal{L}_{GAN}) loss can vary significantly during training, a single static lambda value (e.g. $\lambda = 10$) cannot ensure a fixed balance between loss terms. Instead, we recompute λ dynamically so that the loss terms always maintain a fixed fraction (α) of the total loss. In our experiments, we set $\alpha = 0.10, 0.25, 0.5, 0.75, 0.9$.

As given by the generator loss defined above, to have the reconstruction loss contribute a fraction α of

the total loss, we require:

$$\frac{\lambda \cdot \mathcal{L}_{L1}}{\lambda \cdot \mathcal{L}_{L1} + \mathcal{L}_{GAN}} = \alpha.$$

Solving for λ yields:

$$\lambda = \frac{\alpha \cdot \mathcal{L}_{GAN}}{(1 - \alpha) \cdot \mathcal{L}_{L1}}.$$

Since $\mathcal{L}_{\text{pixel}}$ is in the denominator, if it becomes minimal or zero at any point in the training, it could cause instability or division-by-zero errors. To prevent this, we introduce a small constant ϵ , modifying the equation to:

$$\lambda = \frac{\alpha \cdot \mathcal{L}_{GAN}}{(1 - \alpha) \cdot \mathcal{L}_{\text{pixel}} + \epsilon}.$$

In our implementation, ϵ is set to $1e - 8$, which ensures that even if $\mathcal{L}_{\text{pixel}}$ becomes minuscule, the denominator does not approach zero, avoiding potential numerical errors. The resulting λ value is also clamped between 0.001 and 100 to ensure that any of the variable calculations do not lead to exploding or vanishing gradients that are difficult to propagate through. The computed λ is then applied to the generator loss:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{total}} = \mathcal{L}_{GAN} + \lambda \cdot \mathcal{L}_{L1}.$$

The dynamic λ mechanism is integrated within the training loop, where λ is recalculated at each iteration based on the current values of \mathcal{L}_{GAN} and \mathcal{L}_{L1} , ensuring that both loss terms consistently contribute a set ratio to the total loss.

4 Experiment and Results

4.1 Individual Loss Results

To observe the results of each individual loss independently, two networks were trained separately. One optimizes just for the L1 loss and one optimizes exclusively for the adversarial GAN loss.

Reconstruction (L1) Loss: This model was trained exclusively on attempting to reconstruct the target images on an individual-pixel basis by minimizing the L1 distance between the generated and ground truth images. Although this ensures that the generated output remains close to the actual target in an average sense, it does not enforce sharpness or high-frequency details. As a result, the model tends to produce overly smooth or blurred images, especially

Figure 1: Adversarial (labeled GAN) and Reconstruction losses as only losses

in areas with fine-grained textures, edges, or intricate details. This occurs because L1 loss encourages pixel-wise similarity but does not account for structural or perceptual quality, leading to an averaging effect that fails to capture the complexity of natural images.

Adversarial loss: In this approach, the model was trained using only adversarial loss, without any direct pixel-wise reconstruction objective. The generator's main objective was to produce images that could fool the discriminator, which distinguishes real images from generated ones. Without an explicit pixel-based loss, the model was free to generate more creative and visually sharp images with detailed textures. However, the absence of pixel supervision often led to inconsistencies, such as incorrect local details, unrealistic textures, or mode collapse, where the generator produces a limited variety of output. Although adversarial loss encourages perceptual realism, it alone is also insufficient to ensure accurate content preservation, as the model focuses only on fooling the discriminator rather than being grounded in any sort of real target image.

4.2 Static Loss Weighting

$\lambda = 2.25$: With this λ , the resultant images are clear, yet in most cases deviate from the target images. The features tend to be clear and concise, but the propor-

Figure 2: Example images for static λ values

Figure 3: Losses for static $\lambda = 2.25$

tions of the face or the sizes are slightly off for the human eye (Figure 2).

$\lambda = 6.75$: The results were the most comic-like among all the λ values tested (Figure 2). This highlights a fine balance, where a sufficiently large pixel-wise loss provided strong initial guidance, while still allowing room for the model to explore. The features remained clear, and the proportions were well-preserved due to the relatively strong pixel-wise loss.

$\lambda = 20.25$: With this λ , the resulting images show slight fuzziness and inconsistency (Figure 2). One possible explanation is that the dominant pixel-wise loss disrupts the balance between the generator and the discriminator, preventing them from effectively reinforcing each other. This imbalance may cause the generator to focus too much on local pixel accuracy at the expense of overall coherence, leading to a drop

Figure 4: L1 Loss plotted against λ

in image quality. It underscores the need for careful tuning of λ , ensuring that pixel-wise loss guides the process without undermining the adversarial interplay that drives the GAN toward producing crisp, consistent outputs.

4.3 Dynamic Loss Weighting

As referenced in section 3.3, λ is adjusted in order to maintain a fixed loss contribution of the individual loss terms. As the adversarial loss term stays relatively constant the lambda value begins to follow:

$$\lambda \propto \frac{1}{\mathcal{L}_{\text{pixel}}}$$

where as the L1 loss term decreases as the model learns representations, λ increases proportionally. This relationship can be seen in *Figure 4*.

10% Weight: At 10% weighting, images are suffering from severe mode collapse, with similar artifacts in each generated image. It's evident that giving more weight to Adversarial loss is the main cause of this. This is comparable to the Adversarial (GAN) loss only weighting shown in *Figure 1*.

25% Weight: At 25% weighting, images still seem to have significant artifacts and deformations, similarly to the 10%

50% Weight: This setting produces the most comic-like results among the dynamic lambda generations. Although artifacts remain in a portion of the images (as seen in *Figure 12* in the appendix), the features are clear, and the overall proportions are well-preserved.

75% Weight: Despite relatively sharp features, artifacts and deformations persist, indicating that a higher L1 emphasis with this 75% dynamic lambda weighting didn't seem to eliminate undesirable artifacts.

Figure 5: Loss graphs for dynamic $p = 50\%$

Figure 6: Example images for dynamic λ values

90% Weight: The outputs are noticeably more blurred, with additional smoothing observed. Artifacts remain present, suggesting that an excessive focus on L1 loss with this dynamic lambda approach leads to increased blurriness without fully addressing artifact issues.

Overall, while dynamic loss weighting effectively maintains a target L1 loss contribution throughout training, artifacts persist across all target ratios. The results indicate that there is a trade-off between reducing artifacts and achieving the desired balance between structural fidelity and adversarial realism.

4.4 Ablation Study

As detailed in Section 4.1, both the L1 reconstruction loss and adversarial loss terms are essential components in generating photorealistic results. These loss terms are the key to balancing training stability, image fidelity, and ground truth accuracy. However, the L1 loss converges to generate images with similar pixel values, which builds the model’s understanding of fa-

cial representations, often at the cost of finer facial details.

With these grounding assumptions, we observe this trend across our experiments, where the different static lambda configurations exhibit varying degrees of this detail suppression depending on the L1 weight. We can observe that in Figure 2, when employing a higher weight on the L1 loss the images generated tend to have a more feature smoothing and look marginally blurrier.

Conversely, the dynamic lambda approach, by maintaining a constant ratio, forces the adversarial loss to contribute more consistently throughout training, aiming to mitigate the L1’s tendency to smooth over details. This makes it so that the behavior of the dynamic lambda system generates images that tend toward the adversarial loss only trained model (Figure 1).

During Generative Adversarial Network (GAN) training, the adversarial losses, while often oscillating significantly, generally tend towards an equilibrium state where the generator and discriminator are dynamically balanced (Goodfellow et al., 2014). Due to the way that the network learns using a static lambda introduces an interesting and useful dynamic to the training process. As training progresses, the generator typically improves its ability to reconstruct the target image, causing the absolute value of the L1 loss to decrease substantially. Since λ remains constant, the overall contribution of the $\lambda \times \text{L1 Loss}$ term to the total generator loss diminishes relative to the adversarial GAN loss component, which tends to fluctuate around its equilibrium value. This effectively creates a built-in decay for the impact of the L1 term. The benefit of this implicit annealing is that the L1 loss provides strong structural guidance early in training when the generator’s output is coarse, while allowing the adversarial loss to dominate later, encouraging the refinement of finer details, textures, and stylistic elements necessary to produce outputs that are not just structurally correct but also perceived as realistic or stylistically appropriate by the discriminator.

This dynamic creates a natural balance that helps our models with static lambda values to learn most effectively. We can review the generated images in Figure 2, 6 and see that qualitatively the images developed with static λ values tend to have higher image fidelity, and suffer less from mode collapse and have a higher ground truth link to the original target

images. This is likely due to the lack of L1 loss decay over time. Early in training, when the generator’s output is often noisy or structurally incoherent, the substantial contribution from the L1 term is crucial. It forces the generator to learn the fundamental mapping, capturing the core structure, layout, and color correspondence from the input to the target domain, effectively anchoring the generation process to the ground truth. Without this strong initial guidance focused on reconstruction accuracy, the generator might prematurely prioritize solely fooling the discriminator. This can lead to the optimization process getting stuck in undesirable local minima, turning into mode collapse, where the generator produces only a limited variety of outputs irrespective of the input. This output may not necessarily look like faces but a collection of pixel values that fools the discriminator routinely. This phenomenon is illustrated dramatically in the $p = 10\%$ ($\alpha = 10\%$) example referenced in *Figure 6*, where insufficient structural guidance has led to the generator failing to capture the diversity of the target style and collapsing into repetitive outputs. By ensuring robust pixel-level learning occurs first, the static lambda approach helps the generator establish a diverse and accurate structural foundation before the adversarial loss takes precedence to refine stylistic details and enhance realism.

We can also see that in the other extreme cases where λ is high ($p = 90\%$), that we also experience the negative effects of a high L1 weighting where we are building blurred representations of images without high feature accuracy. This dynamic approach takes the negatives from either side of the weighting as it does not benefit from the natural decay that exists as the network learns the pixel representations in the target images.

Both *Figure 3* and *Figure 5* show that as the network trains, the respective losses are extremely fickle. These fluctuations, particularly the sharp, transient spikes prominently visible in the Discriminator Loss, Generator Loss, and consequently the GAN Loss component (*Figure 3*), are characteristic artifacts frequently encountered during the training of Generative Adversarial Networks (GANs) (Goodfellow et al., 2014). Such pronounced oscillations stem directly from the adversarial nature of the training, where the generator (G) and discriminator (D) networks are locked in a competitive co-evolution. The training dynamics do not always proceed smoothly towards a sta-

ble equilibrium; instead, they often exhibit periods of instability (Salimans et al., 2016). A large spike in the Generator’s loss, for instance, often signifies a moment where the Discriminator has substantially improved its ability to identify generated fakes, perhaps by learning a particularly discriminative feature. This heightened capability of the Discriminator poses a significantly harder challenge for the Generator, causing its loss (measuring its failure to fool the Discriminator) to increase sharply until it adapts its strategy (Arjovsky et al., 2017). Similarly, shifts in the Discriminator’s loss can occur as it rapidly adapts to new, potentially more challenging, outputs from the Generator. This cyclical dynamic, where improvements in one network provoke adaptations and potential temporary setbacks in the other, is a hallmark of the non-cooperative game underlying GAN training and explains the recurrent, spiky behavior observed in the loss curves, a phenomenon widely acknowledged in GAN literature (Salimans et al., 2016) and (Arjovsky et al., 2017).

While the broader oscillations reflect the standard competitive dynamic, the observed large, sharp, and highly transient spikes in loss, particularly evident in the GAN and Generator loss plots (*Figure 3*, *Figure 5*), signify moments of acute, temporary instability within the training process. These abrupt surges, which rapidly subside in subsequent steps, can be interpreted as points where the complex, high-dimensional optimization landscape is particularly challenging. For instance, the Generator might momentarily produce a batch of outputs containing artifacts that the Discriminator finds exceptionally easy to identify, leading to a dramatic, short-lived increase in the Generator’s adversarial loss (Arjovsky et al., 2017). Conversely, the Discriminator might briefly latch onto a highly effective but ultimately unstable distinguishing strategy, causing a spike.

These events are often related to the stochastic nature of the training (e.g., the specific mini-batch sampled) interacting with the non-convexity of the GAN objective function (Goodfellow et al., 2014). The optimization algorithm (like Adam) might take a step into a region causing a temporary but significant performance drop for one of the networks. The rapid recovery following such a spike suggests that either the opposing network quickly adapts, or the optimizer navigates past this localized region of instability, allowing the loss to return promptly towards its previ-

ous downward trajectory. Such transient instabilities are not uncommon in deep learning and particularly in GANs, where the objective function landscape is known to be complex and potentially fraught with sharp gradients or local optima that can momentarily disrupt the learning process (Salimans et al., 2016).

5 Social Impact of ComicGAN

The importance of writing about the impact that artificial intelligence, like ComicGAN, has on the world is increasing day by day. For that reason, we would like to dedicate this section to explaining some positive and negative implications image generation models, specifically ComicGAN, have on our society as a whole.

To start, ComicGAN has the potential to support artists, content creators, and visual designers with a versatile tool that simply and quickly accelerates the design of comic-book style images. To give an example, this increase in speed could help teachers working in the creative sector to more quickly provide examples on how to draw and provide personal examples per student. Furthermore, for those students or anyone who is not an artist, this visual artificial intelligence allows people to express themselves artistically, without the barrier of actually requiring creative skills. Moreover, this technology that transforms everyday portraits into comic-book-style imagery would help those non-creative people to reimagine their identity in a new way, which could light the spark in their artistic journey. This could slightly bind the gap between creative and non-creative people, fostering greater inclusivity.

However, with this new technology, ComicGAN also carries some potential risks. These risks include, among others, the potential of the model’s training set being biased, i.e. the model may cause or increase harmful stereotypes related to race, sex, or other characteristics in the generated faces. These data sets should be well tested according to these biases before being rolled out to the public. Furthermore, people may use the technology on other people without asking for consent, which could violate personal privacy and image rights.

6 Discussion

6.1 Key Insights

Our experiments reveal several key insights into optimizing Pix2Pix for comic image translation, particu-

larly concerning the influence of static and dynamic λ adjustments on training convergence and output quality.

The dynamic lambda adjustment approach demonstrates a clear ability to influence the balance between adversarial and reconstruction losses throughout the training process. By dynamically adjusting λ , the model consistently maintains a pre-defined ratio between the two losses. This is particularly beneficial in preventing the L1 loss from dominating the adversarial loss, potentially leading to over-smoothed results. Our findings suggest that a balanced static approach, such as a low L1 loss contribution between 2-10, produces the most visually appealing comic images. This balance allows the model to retain essential structural information while incorporating stylistic elements crucial to the comic aesthetic. While balancing which elements of the loss are significant at different stages of training by following a natural decay process.

We’ve found that simply balancing the loss ratio does not guarantee optimal results. In our ablation study, we found that solely optimizing the adversarial or reconstruction loss produced good but worse results than pre-defined λ values. The reconstruction loss lead to a significant loss of finer details while the adversarial loss resulted in a lack of ground truth accuracy. This is a common theme within GAN-based training as the two models push each other to optimize. We found that the static lambda values benefited from an annealing process, where the L1 term acted to guide the early training phase.

6.2 Limitations

Despite the promising results, several limitations need to be addressed. One potential issue is the risk of overfitting, especially when training on smaller datasets. While the dataset used contained 10,000 pairs of images, there is still significant model deviation. Furthermore, the complexity introduced by dynamically scheduling λ can be challenging to manage. Determining appropriate ratios for the target L1 contribution requires careful tuning, as demonstrated by the varying image qualities across different dynamic λ configurations. Finding values is difficult as too much or too little weight on either leads to a host of problems. Furthermore, we can see that as the network trains, the respective losses are extremely fickle with periods of high and low optimization. These

fluctuations stem directly from the adversarial nature of the training, where the generator and discriminator networks are locked in a competitive co-evolution.

7 Conclusion

In this paper, we presented ComicGAN, a modified Pix2Pix-based framework geared toward translating facial images into comic-style visuals. Our primary objective was to investigate the effect of static vs dynamic weighting of the pixel-wise reconstruction and adversarial losses. Through a systematic exploration of different λ configurations, we have shown that:

- A purely adversarial setup produced crisp but structurally inconsistent outputs, while a purely pixel-wise L1 approach yielded faithful yet overly smoothed and blurry images. static λ bvalues
- Static lambda values benefited from an implicit “annealing” process, where the L1 term dominantly guided early training and then gradually ceded ground to the adversarial term, resulting in more coherent and sharper comic translations.
- Dynamic lambda strategies enforced a fixed ratio of adversarial to reconstruction loss throughout training. Although they successfully maintained a desired balance, certain high-frequency artifacts remained stubbornly present. The best outputs appeared at a moderate ratio (e.g., 50% L1), while extremely low or high L1 ratios yielded either mode collapse or excessive blurring.

These findings show that balancing adversarial and L1 reconstruction objectives is a pivotal point in GAN based image-to-image translation tasks. While a dynamic λ can stabilize the relative contributions of each loss function, the resulting images can inherit some of the less desirable artifact characteristic of exclusively adversarially driven training. Meanwhile, the static λ values appear to take advantage of natural GAN training dynamics—providing clear structural pixel-wise guidance at the beginning and allowing the adversarial loss to take effect and fine-tune the stylistic details later.

7.1 Future Research

Future research might examine strategies that combine static and dynamic lambda scheduling—e.g. beginning with a higher fixed λ to ensure a good struc-

tural baseline then only switching to a dynamic schedule when training stabilizes.

Integrating multiscale loss terms (Zhao et al., 2019) could be a possible approach which holds considerable promise for improving both the structural integrity and the detail richness of the generated comic images. This approach entails computing the loss not just on the final output image but also on downsampled versions of both the generated and target images. This allows the model to effectively learn representations at different levels of abstraction. For example, a high-resolution loss term would focus on capturing fine-grained details like individual lines and shading variations, while a low-resolution loss term would encourage the generator to maintain the overall structure and proportions of the face. Specifically, this could be achieved by incorporating a pyramidal loss structure where the generated and target images are progressively downsampled, and the L1 and/or adversarial loss is calculated at each scale. The final loss would be a weighted sum of the losses computed at each level, allowing for precise control over the emphasis placed on different levels of detail. Furthermore, the discriminator could also be adapted to operate at multiple scales, allowing it to distinguish real and fake images based on both global structure and local details. Such a multiscale discriminator might involve a series of convolutional layers with varying receptive field sizes, allowing it to capture features at different spatial resolutions.

Additional enhancements could include the development of a meta-learner that automatically adjusts hyperparameters (e.g. λ) based on the generators outputs each epoch. Instead of a strict value or set loss weighting as tested in this paper, one could train a secondary model, (often called a *controller* or a *hypernetwork*) that observes real-time metrics such as image sharpness, the presence of artifacts, and mode collapse prevalence to fine-tune the weighting of adversarial vs. L1 reconstruction losses. This approach builds on recent research into hypernetworks (Ha et al., 2017), which are networks designed to generate or modify the hyperparameters of another network. In the context of ComicGAN, a hypernetwork could be trained to output an adaptive λ value at each training step, conditioned on image features or loss values from the generator or discriminator. Such a system would eliminate the need for manually designed static or rule-based dynamic schedules and allow for

real-time correction of issues, maximizing the output of the network. This would mark a significant step toward making GAN training more autonomous, robust, and adaptable to different datasets.

Finally, extending the methodology to other artistic styles beyond comic art could broaden ComicGAN's applicability. This would involve training the model on datasets encompassing various artistic styles, enabling it to translate images into a wider range of visual aesthetics.

8 References

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9 Appendix

9.1 Model Implementation

9.1.1 Generator Model

```
1 class Generator(nn.Module):
2     def __init__(self, in_channels=3, out_channels=3,
3         num_residual_blocks=4):
4         super(Generator, self).__init__()
5         self.down_convolution_1 = downsample_block(
6             in_channels, 64, use_batchnorm=False)
7         self.down_convolution_2 = downsample_block(64,
8             128)
9         self.down_convolution_3 = downsample_block(128,
10            256)
11        self.down_convolution_4 = downsample_block(256,
12            512)
13        self.down_convolution_5 = downsample_block(512,
14            512)
15        self.down_convolution_6 = downsample_block(512,
16            512)
17        self.down_convolution_7 = downsample_block(512,
18            512)
19        self.down_convolution_8 = downsample_block(512,
20            512)
21
22        self.res_blocks = nn.Sequential(*[ResidualBlock
23            (512) for _ in range(num_residual_blocks)
24        ])
25
26        self.up_convolution_1 = upsample_block(512,
27            512, use_dropout=True)
28        self.up_convolution_2 = upsample_block(1024,
29            512, use_dropout=True)
30        self.up_convolution_3 = upsample_block(1024,
31            512, use_dropout=True)
32        self.up_convolution_4 = upsample_block(1024,
33            512)
34        self.up_convolution_5 = upsample_block(1024,
35            256)
36        self.up_convolution_6 = upsample_block(512,
37            128)
38        self.up_convolution_7 = upsample_block(256, 64)
39
40        self.final = nn.Sequential(
41            nn.Upsample(scale_factor=2),
42            nn.ZeroPad2d((1, 0, 1, 0)),
43            nn.Conv2d(128, out_channels, kernel_size=4,
44                padding=1),
45            nn.Tanh())
46
47    def forward(self, x):
48        down_1 = self.down_convolution_1(x)
49        down_2 = self.down_convolution_2(down_1)
50        down_3 = self.down_convolution_3(down_2)
51        down_4 = self.down_convolution_4(down_3)
52        down_5 = self.down_convolution_5(down_4)
53        down_6 = self.down_convolution_6(down_5)
54        down_7 = self.down_convolution_7(down_6)
55        down_8 = self.down_convolution_8(down_7)
56
57        res = self.res_blocks(down_8)
58
59        up_1 = self.up_convolution_1(res)
60        up_1 = torch.cat([up_1, down_7], 1)
61        up_2 = self.up_convolution_2(up_1)
62        up_2 = torch.cat([up_2, down_6], 1)
63        up_3 = self.up_convolution_3(up_2)
64        up_3 = torch.cat([up_3, down_5], 1)
65        up_4 = self.up_convolution_4(up_3)
66        up_4 = torch.cat([up_4, down_4], 1)
67        up_5 = self.up_convolution_5(up_4)
68        up_5 = torch.cat([up_5, down_3], 1)
69        up_6 = self.up_convolution_6(up_5)
70        up_6 = torch.cat([up_6, down_2], 1)
71        up_7 = self.up_convolution_7(up_6)
72        up_7 = torch.cat([up_7, down_1], 1)
73        up_8 = self.final(up_7)
74        return up_8
```

9.1.2 Discriminator Model

```
1 class Discriminator(nn.Module):
2     def __init__(self):
3         super(Discriminator, self).__init__()
4
5         self.model = nn.Sequential(
6             nn.Conv2d(6, 64, kernel_size=4, stride=2,
7                 padding=1),
8             nn.LeakyReLU(0.2, inplace=True),
9             nn.Conv2d(64, 128, kernel_size=4, stride=2,
10                padding=1),
11            nn.BatchNorm2d(128),
12            nn.LeakyReLU(0.2, inplace=True),
13            nn.Conv2d(128, 256, kernel_size=4, stride
14                =2, padding=1),
15            nn.BatchNorm2d(256),
16            nn.LeakyReLU(0.2, inplace=True),
17            nn.Conv2d(256, 512, kernel_size=4, stride
18                =2, padding=1),
19            nn.BatchNorm2d(512),
20            nn.LeakyReLU(0.2, inplace=True),
21            nn.Conv2d(512, 1, kernel_size=4, stride=1,
22                padding=0),
23            nn.Sigmoid(), # Add Sigmoid for BCELoss)
24
25    def forward(self, x):
26        return self.model(x)
27
28    \subsubsection{Static Loss Calculation}
29    \begin{lstlisting}[style=pythonstyle]
30    criterion_GAN = nn.BCELoss()
31    criterion_pixelwise = nn.L1Loss()
32    lam = 2.25
33
34    def discriminator_loss(D_real, D_fake):
35        real_loss = criterion_GAN(D_real, torch.ones_like(
36            D_real))
37        fake_loss = criterion_GAN(D_fake, torch.zeros_like(
38            D_fake))
39        return (real_loss + fake_loss) * 0.5
40
41    def generator_loss(D_fake, gen_output, target):
42        gan_loss = criterion_GAN(D_fake, torch.ones_like(
43            D_fake)) # Try to fool the discriminator
44        pixelwise_loss = criterion_pixelwise(gen_output,
45            target)
46        return [gan_loss + (lam * pixelwise_loss), gan_loss
47            , pixelwise_loss]
```

9.1.3 Static Loss Calculation

```
1 criterion_GAN = nn.BCELoss()
2 criterion_pixelwise = nn.L1Loss()
3 lam = 2.25
4
5 def discriminator_loss(D_real, D_fake):
6     real_loss = criterion_GAN(D_real, torch.ones_like(
7         D_real))
8     fake_loss = criterion_GAN(D_fake, torch.zeros_like(
9         D_fake))
10    return (real_loss + fake_loss) * 0.5
11
12 def generator_loss(D_fake, gen_output, target):
13     gan_loss = criterion_GAN(D_fake, torch.ones_like(
14         D_fake)) # Try to fool the discriminator
15     pixelwise_loss = criterion_pixelwise(gen_output,
16         target)
17     return [gan_loss + (lam * pixelwise_loss), gan_loss
18         , pixelwise_loss] # Weighted sum of GAN loss
19         and pixelwise L1 loss
```

9.1.4 Dynamic Loss Calculation

```
1 criterion_GAN = nn.BCELoss()
2 criterion_pixelwise = nn.L1Loss()
3 target_ratio = 0.9
4
5 def compute_dynamic_lambda(L_GAN, L_pixel, target_ratio):
6     epsilon = 1e-8 # Small constant for numerical
7     stability
8     lam = (target_ratio * L_GAN) / ((1 - target_ratio)
9     * L_pixel + epsilon)
10    return torch.clamp(lam, min=1e-3, max=100) #11
11    Clamps lambda between 1e-3 and 100)
12
13 def discriminator_loss(D_real, D_fake):
14    real_loss = criterion_GAN(D_real, torch.ones_like(
15    D_real))
16    fake_loss = criterion_GAN(D_fake, torch.zeros_like(
17    D_fake))
18    return (real_loss + fake_loss) * 0.5
19
20 def generator_loss(D_fake, gen_output, target):
21    gan_loss = criterion_GAN(D_fake, torch.ones_like(
22    D_fake)) # Fool the discriminator
23    pixelwise_loss = criterion_pixelwise(gen_output,
24    target)
25
26    # Compute dynamic lambda
27    lam = compute_dynamic_lambda(gan_loss,
28    pixelwise_loss, target_ratio)
29
30    return [gan_loss + (lam * pixelwise_loss), gan_loss
31    , pixelwise_loss, lam]
```

9.1.5 Training Loop Implementation

```
def train(num_epochs=10):
    loss_file = 'losses.csv'
    # Create CSV file and write headers if it doesn't exist
    if not os.path.exists(loss_file):
        with open(loss_file, mode='w', newline='') as f:
            writer = csv.writer(f)
            writer.writerow(["Epoch", "Step", "D_Loss", "G_Loss", "
                Gan_Loss", "Pixelwise_Loss", "Lambda"])
    for epoch in range(num_epochs):
        epoch_progress = tqdm(enumerate(train_loader), total=len(
            train_loader), desc=f"Epoch_{epoch+1}/{num_epochs}",
            position=0, leave=True)
        for i, (real_images, target_images) in epoch_progress:
            real_images = real_images.to(device)
            target_images = target_images.to(device)
            # Generate fake images
            fake_images = generator(real_images)
            # Train Discriminator
            optimizer_D.zero_grad()
            D_real = discriminator(torch.cat([real_images,
                target_images], 1))
            D_fake = discriminator(torch.cat([real_images,
                fake_images.detach()], 1))
            D_loss = discriminator_loss(D_real, D_fake)
            D_loss.backward()
            optimizer_D.step()
            # Train Generator
            optimizer_G.zero_grad()
            D_fake = discriminator(torch.cat([real_images,
                fake_images], 1))
            G_loss = generator_loss(D_fake, fake_images,
                target_images)
            G_loss[0].backward()
            optimizer_G.step()
            # Save losses to CSV file
            with open(loss_file, mode='a', newline='') as f:
                writer = csv.writer(f)
                writer.writerow([epoch+1, i, D_loss.item(), G_loss
                    [0].item(), G_loss[1].item(), G_loss[2].item(),
                    G_loss[3].item()])
            # Update tqdm progress bar with loss values
            epoch_progress.set_postfix({"D_Loss": D_loss.item(), "G_
                Loss": G_loss[0].item(), "GanLoss": G_loss[1].item
                (), "PixelLoss": G_loss[2].item(), "Lambda": G_loss
                [3].item()})
        print_and_save_images(real_images, 5, epoch, i, title="Real_
            Images", save_dir="real_images", filename_prefix="real")
        print_and_save_images(fake_images, 5, epoch, i, title="
            Generated_Images", save_dir="generated_images",
            filename_prefix="fake")
        print_and_save_images(target_images, 5, epoch, i, title="
            Target_Images", save_dir="target_images",
            filename_prefix="target")
        os.makedirs("models/generator", exist_ok=True)
        os.makedirs("models/discriminator", exist_ok=True)
        # Save model to retrieve earlier versions if needed
        torch.save(generator.module.state_dict() if hasattr(generator
            , "module") else generator.state_dict(), f'/kaggle/
            working/models/generator/generator_epoch{epoch}.pth')
        torch.save(discriminator.module.state_dict() if hasattr(
            discriminator, "module") else discriminator.state_dict()
            , f'/kaggle/working/models/discriminator/
            discriminator_epoch{epoch}.pth')
        torch.save(optimizer_G.state_dict(), f'optimizer_G{epoch}.pth
            ')
        torch.save(optimizer_D.state_dict(), f'optimizer_D{epoch}.pth
            ')
    
```


Fig 7: Static λ with value (2.25)

Fig 11: Dynamic λ with value (25%)

Fig 8: Static λ with value (6.75)

Fig 12: Dynamic λ with value (50%)

Fig 9: Static λ with value (20.25)

Fig 13: Dynamic λ with value (75%)

Fig 10: Dynamic λ with value (10%)

Fig 14: Dynamic λ with value (90%)